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**THE TRADITION OF GURU KELUCHARAN MAHAPATRA
AND ITS EVOLUTION INTO PRESENT SUB STYLES**

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NATURE OF PROJECT

One of the pioneers in the revival and establishment of Odissi dance from almost oblivion to the stature of a Classical dance style of India, Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra is one of the four Gurus who made Odissi a globally recognized dance form. The most renowned of all the Gurus, Guruji's style of Odissi gained tremendous popularity due to its vast propagation through his innumerable students.

Today, some of his distinguished disciples, inspired by his vision, have reinvented the traditional form and developed their distinct styles using their individual aesthetic sensibilities, which can convincingly be termed as Sub styles of Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra style of Odissi. Currently, six sub styles are distinctly identified, initiated by Madhavi Mudgal, Sharmila Biswas, Ileana Citaristi, Nrityagram, Jhelum Paranjape, and Srjan - where the legacy of Guruji's style continues under Ratikant Mahapatra who simultaneously is also developing a sub style of his own.

And over time - influenced also by regional traditions, rituals, lifestyles and practices – each of these sub styles, with specific codification w.r.t. grammar and technique, are gradually maturing into ally-traditions by themselves.

NECESSITY OF SUCH A PROJECT

In the present dance scene, with the focus increasingly shifting towards group choreographic work and with the urge to create and present new works by existing choreographers, the practice, teaching and performance of solo works, particularly those created by Guruji, are gradually losing significance. As a result of this, the dancers of present generation are increasingly finding it difficult to correlate the continuity of Guruji's tradition to the ones that are evolving today from it.

It is this continuity of one tradition within several emerging ones and the progressive transformation of a sub style into a tradition in itself, is what I want to study and explore.

With this view in mind, the purpose of my research or study is three fold.

First, study the distinct features of the above-mentioned sub styles separately.

Second, revisit some unique solo works of Guruji in each sub style with the technique taught and practiced in each.

Third, do a comparative study of the sub styles in terms of grammar and technique and also understand how the solo works of Guruji have been influenced by the individual aesthetics of each sub style.

This will also provide insight to the triggering point for the need to reinvent an existing tradition, which over time and with a fresh approach, leads to the birth of a new one.

INTRODUCTION

Every competent artist, with a thirst for knowledge and a will to rid her art of parochialism and complacency, goes through a very significant and inevitable transitory phase from collective participation to individual pursuit; in case of a dancer, from working within an ensemble to venturing out as a soloist. I think a lot of it has to do with the dancer's intellect. Beyond the physicality of the dance, when the mind begins to yearn for the 'tripti' or total satisfaction brought about by complete synergy of the mind, body and soul over and above the immediate trivial concerns of movement technique, when the 'utsah' of a movement stems from the emotion driving it so much so that the body feels just right at the said moment, in perfect harmony with the mind, in response to the 'bhava' initiating the movement, that is when the dancer intuitively knows that it is time and that she is ready to start her individual pursuit, searching both within and outside herself, to find her own personal vision that would define her art. Because every work of art ultimately becomes a true reflection of the artist herself.

One can never point out the exact moment when this transition starts, but when it does, the dancer invariably chooses solitude and moves away from the busyness of dance in order to introspect. And it is necessary to introspect. Because then, one begins to observe the subtle intricacies embedded in nature and life around us, to recognise and acknowledge one's own strengths and weaknesses, likes and dislikes, to discard unnecessary inhibitions and obligations, all of which eventually giving birth to an aesthetic sensibility which is personal and is reflected not only in the kind of music, literature, poetry, texture, colour, movement, shapes and forms that she identifies herself with but also in the ordinary routine of her everyday life, so much so that an understated finesse inherent to our culture emanates from her manner, word and most importantly, her art.

I think that moment came to me five years back. I cannot tell exactly when in time, but I do remember this nagging feeling of restlessness which I couldn't shake off, much as I tried, and it seemed to grow on me, compelling me to discard

affiliations, drawing me towards empty spaces – both physically and emotionally – almost like starting all over again on an empty canvas.

I remember struggling to fight this overwhelming need to break free until finally, unable to hold back, I took a giant leap of faith into the unknown, to discover the new and rediscover the old, to assimilate and incorporate, in search of my own vision of Odissi which would eventually help fulfill my creative aspirations not merely as a dazzling performer on stage but as an individual artist of refined sensibilities with a distinct language of her own. In Chandralekha's words, "For me, to be able to respond to the realities of life is as crucial as to remain alive and tuned to sensuality and cultural wealth. I have struggled to harmonise, to integrate these diverging directions in order to remain sensitive and whole."

With classical dances being increasingly represented as group choreographies, perhaps I am moving against the current. But because I firmly believe that the soul of Indian classical dances rests within the solo form rather than its group manifestations, the choice of an independent path seemed inevitable.

FIRST REPORT

I have often asked myself during the course of the past four years, why am I so convinced that my own dance will emerge from searching and digging into the creative endeavours of Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra and why do I feel this continuous need to carry on this endless search despite meagre resources at my dispense. It would be apt to quote Dr Priyambada Mohanty Hejmadi from her review of Dr. Ileana Citaristi's book *The Making of a Guru* published in the November 2002 issue of Sangeet Natak Akademi's journal, for therein lies the answer to why Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra is such an indispensable subject for discussion, debate and retrospection in the world of Odissi, a subject that needs to be researched upon with much sincerity and in utmost detail–

“If one has to assess the contribution of Guru Kelucharan to Odissi Dance, one has also to take into account the role of other artists in his development. What really puts Kelucharan apart from all his contemporaries is his ability to imbibe, synthesize and harmonize ideas from various sources. As I have mentioned earlier, his association with Pandit Bhubaneswar Mishra was both timely and lucky. As Kelucharan's work with Bhubaneswar Babu progressed, the Pallavis became more and more musically complex and ornate, and in the process some masterpieces were created. Sanjukta Panigrahi too played a crucial role in a later phase by bringing precision to Kelucharan's choreography. In her guru's own words, 'I cannot create another Sanjukta'. Thus, while the story of Odissi is the story of its gurus, it is also that of students through whom the dance expressed itself.”

My research is essentially premised on the very last line - that the story of Odissi is also of his students, some of whom have distinctly created an individualistic style of their own. And yes, it is also centred upon his many intricate compositions of Pallavis which, as I delve deeper into their

aesthetically linked musical and rhythmic patterns, seem to me as the fountainhead of the guiding principles of his creative process.

My work plan states that I will spend about six months with one of his disciple-choreographers and understand from them how Guru Kelucharan has influenced their life and art as also their individual creative process and aesthetic sensibilities. In the past one year I have spent considerable time with Dr. Ileana Citaristi, as and when we could both work out our individual schedules to meet, staying at her house, watching her teach, practise and perform.

From 2012 to 2013, I was able to visit and spend time with Madhavi Mudgal for the same reason.

My association with Sharmila Biswas from 2008 till 2012 as Administrator, Faculty Member and Senior Repertory Dancer acquainted me with Sharmilaji's stylistic peculiarities.

Through my training at Nrityagram (1998-2004), I have imbibed the elements typical to the Nrityagram style.

I shall briefly explain the stylistic differences as I have observed and understood among these schools of Odissi which teach, practise and perform in Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra's style of Odissi -

NRITYAGRAM STYLE

In order to understand and appreciate the Nrityagram style, one has to acquaint oneself with the training regime that is followed there. Here, I speak of the routine I followed for 6 years – 1998 till 2004, that which moulded not just my body but also my mind into those of a professional dancer.

BASIC TRAINING:

The first three years focused on preparing the body for Odissi through intensive muscle conditioning programme and on perfecting the basic technique of the dance.

DAILY ROUTINE:

We followed a gruelling daily schedule of 15-16 hours, beginning at 5.30 in the morning with a 4 Km jog. Next, after having swept and mopped the dance hall, a body conditioning session continued for an hour and a half focusing on strengthening and flexibility using yoga, Pilates, Kalaripayattu, Modern Dance technique and traditional exercises. Breakfast followed, after which the intense

training of Odissi basics continued up to 3 hours. This was followed by lunch after which each student was assigned work for the community – be it office, the kitchen or taking care of guest accommodation. I was the community food manager for 3 years, looked after the library for all 6 years, did accommodation work for a few months and worked in the office throughout taking care of press & publicity material, document filing, updation of contacts, daily accounts and liaising with organisations for performances.

In the evenings, we worked in the fields weeding, watering plants, digging the soil, sowing seeds – growing our own vegetables. After tea, we worked on our individual corrections for an hour before coming back to class for evening practice and later to observe seniors practise.

ADVANCED TRAINING:

I joined the ensemble in 2001 and simultaneously graduated to the next three years of advanced training, in which I learnt the subtle nuances typical to Odissi and performance skills under Surupa Sen.

I was also appointed teacher in the same year and began teaching the body conditioning class in the mornings and Odissi basics to the juniors in the evenings before ensemble practice. I also started teaching in Nrityagram's village outreach programme training hundreds of local village children and later in the city outreach programme teaching for 6 hours every Sunday.

We worked for 6 days a week practising 8 to 10 hours everyday. On the weekly off day, we would cook our own food, clean our rooms, wash piles of soiled clothes and sleep.

WORKSHOPS ATTENDED:

In the 6 years of training, various workshops given by artists visiting or invited to Nrityagram further honed my body and intellect to evolve into a better dancer.

Each workshop was an eye opener.

Abhinaya by Smt. Kalanidhi Narayan, the greatest living legend of expressional dance in India today, taught me the language of eyes and its importance in Indian classical dance. I learned to speak with my eyes.

Chhau, a martial art form from Orissa & Bengal, taught me balance and grace. Movements drawn from day to day village life of Orissa such as cowdung mixing, grinding turmeric and so on familiarized me with the essence of their culture, their art of living.

A crucial workshop on Movement analysis, Choreography and Alexander

Technique by Mahesh Mehboobani, noted choreographer, built the foundation for my understanding of movement, teaching me to identify the intention behind it, its energy, its execution. He taught me how to visualise a movement and then relate it to my body. I learnt about weight and weightlessness, about organic and inorganic movement.

Dr. Kannan Pugazhendi, a leading sports doctor, taught me the importance of correct breathing while in movement through Chi-Gung and also to developing strength, stamina, lightness in the body through Kalaripayattu.

Workshops on Movement, Theater, Voice & Gesture by Wolfgang Hoffman and Theater der Klaenge from Germany revealed to me the interrelation between dance and theatre, its differences, taught me contact improvisation, working with body weight, the difference between narration about a character and its personification.

Modern dance technique by Alexis Major from USA taught me extension of limbs through tonduis, plies and batmas, balancing body weight using upper body instead of legs through handstands and cartwheels, strengthening core muscles using Graham & Limon technique.

Workshop on physiotherapy and prevention of injury by Dr. Kannan improved my muscle awareness, I learned to listen to my body and its needs, I learned the importance of a systematic cooling down through specific stretching after an intense dance practice to prevent injury resulting from sudden contraction of fatigued muscles.

Training in different styles of Odissi under prominent gurus like Ramani Ranjan Jena (India), Ramli Ibrahim (Malaysia), Sangeeta Dash (India) and Dr. Ratna Roy (USA) familiarized me with the uniqueness of the styles of three great Gurus and architects of present Odissi dance – late Guru Kelucharan Mohapatra, late Guru Debaprasad Das and late Guru Pankajcharan Das.

Many other workshops, equally relevant to my growth, followed.

With this intensive training programme as my foundation, I travelled extensively with the Nrityagram Dance Ensemble giving over 300 performances both in India and USA, over 250 lecture-demonstrations to visiting students, domestic and foreign tourists, at museums, universities and schools across India and North America and teaching master classes to dance students and professionals while on tour.

This rigor in training and consecutive ensemble work with Nrityagram for 8 years has given me a thorough understanding of the Nrityagram approach to

Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra's parent style. I have studied not only the basics of their style but, because I was part of their choreographic works, I was also able to learn pallavi or pure dance and abhinaya, both of Guruji's composition and of Surupa Sen's which highlighted the distinctiveness of the Nrityagram technique.

Among Kelu Guruji's compositions, I want to focus on Saveri pallavi as nritta and Tolagi Gopodando as abhinaya which distinctly highlight Nrityagram's technique and movement approach. DVD with the same was submitted earlier.

Among Surupa Sen's compositions, Akriti or Malkauns pallavi as nritta and Shivashtakam as abhinaya have extensive incorporation of the charis (akasha and bhumi) and karanas of the Natyashastra into the Odissi technique. I do not have copies of their videos but one can view these pieces online at pad.ma –

<https://pad.ma/BDR/player/00:06:22.840> (akriti)

<https://pad.ma/AXG/player/00:00:10.120> (shivashtakam)

To me, the Nrityagram technique is more expansive and broad, made possible through the assimilation of such elements into the form as yogic postures, kalaripayattu, modern dance techniques and the charis of the Natyashastra.

Some illustrations will help understand this better as follows –

11
Sit down
raising
arms up
(4 counts)

12
Stand
up
with arms
raised above
head
(4 counts)

13
Come up
bringing
arms down
in front
(4 counts)

14
Finish in
standing position
opening arms to
the side
(4 counts)

= SEQUENCE WITH TONDUI

side view

Feet together

side view

Foot to
front,
hands at
waist

front view

Foot to
the side

side view

Foot to
the back

hip remains closed and
facing front

- Entire foot is brushed out along the floor to the maximum pointed position
- Upper body remains absolutely still, stomach muscles engaged in moving the whole leg
- First brush foot to front 8 times, then to side 8 times keeping knee facing front, then backwards 8 times
- Finish all sides with one leg and then change to other leg.

(B) BHUMI CHARIS FROM NATYASHASTRA

= STHITAVARTA (स्थितावर्ता)

1
Extended
leg circles
in front of
other foot

2
3
Final position has
hip and shoulders facing front
with maximum twist at waist,
circling leg finishes on toes.

Ayona Bhaskar

= SHAKATASYA TATHEIVACHA (शकटास्य तथैव च) (3)

1 Lunge forward and arch back with hands going up

2 Stretch arms up while sitting down

3 Scoop over and down to touch nose to floor

4 Arch out and up with palms on floor

5 releasing palms off the floor to get up with chest leading the movement. Draw back leg in to Samapada.

6

7

© ĀKASHA CHĀRIS FROM NATYASHASTRA

= ATIKRANTA (अतिक्रान्ता)

1 Right leg up in Bandhani pada

2 Stretch right knee to the front

3 Jump forward on right foot while lifting left leg off the floor keeping hip closed throughout

= PĀRSHVAKRANTA (पार्श्वक्रान्ता)

1 Lolita pada

2 Stretch raised knee with toes pointed

3 Flex foot to bring down

4 heel on floor with straightened knee

5 Pull opposite leg in to join heels together

= SUCHI (सूची)

1 Bandhani pada to the front

2 Stretch knee & leg to side

3 lower leg to floor

4 Pull opposite leg in to bring feet together

Ajaykumar

SHARMILA BISWAS' STYLE

My association and collaborative work with Sharmila Biswas as repertory member and faculty member at Odissi Vision and Movement Centre for next 4 years has familiarised me with Sharmilaji's approach. Apart from the basics I learnt at Nrityagram, at OVM I learnt a new set of chowk, tribhangi, bharamari, chari which they practise as their basic steps. And because Sharmilaji's work draws largely from the folk traditions of Orissa, being part of the repertory, I was involved in her translation of folk movements into Odissi, retaining the spirit of the folk movement while restructuring it in the Odissi technique, which eventually led to the creation of a pallavi – Gati Bilas, which distinctly highlights her movement approach. For abhinaya, I worked with her on creating a solo piece from its group production – Katha Surpanakha and also an ashatapadi, both her compositions. Videos of Gati Bilas and Katha Surpanakha as a group choreography and also of Katha Surpanakha as a solo piece performed by me have been sent earlier.

With Sharmilaji, I was involved only in new choreographic works. I did not get the opportunity to learn any of Guruji's compositions from her.

To me, the movement approach of Sharmilaji is free and open, sometimes loud in movement and expression, not so strictly bound within strong grammar allowing space for innovation, much like the folk forms, particularly of Odisha from which she draws inspiration. Having said so, my limited exposure to her teaching of folk movements in class has convinced me that of the fact that folk movements require a considerable degree of maturity for being executed in their right spirit and at times may also be considered the source of some typical Odissi dance movements. In her own words, her approach is more impish. I would call it more extrovert, made more so with her extensive use of sets, props and elaborate costumes for conveying the content of her concept in the choreography. So her portrayal of a Khandita Radha would be very different from that of Nrityagram or Madhavi Mudgal.

One could refer to the following link on Youtube in which I was able to demonstrate some of Sharmilaji's Odissi movements translated from folk movements: www.youtube.com/watch?v=9O8AbiRivCQ

MADHAVI MUDGAL STYLE

My year long learning under Madhavi Mudgal has familiarised me with her teaching methods, more specifically her understanding of the basics of Odissi and her approach to abhinaya through ashtapadis. With her, I learnt yet another set of chowk and tribhangi which she uses as the basis of the movement approach specific to her style. I also learnt two of Guruji's ashtapadi compositions – Priye Charushile and Dheera Sameere, which brought an understanding to her approach in abhinaya. And I watched her teach, practise, choreograph and perform through which I was able to better understand her aesthetic sensibilities in music and dance and how she brings both together, technically, visually and aurally.

I did not learn any of Madhaviji's compositions but watched her students practise Ragamalika pallavi created by her which distinctly highlights her movement approach in response to music. I wish to document this pallavi and also her basic steps performed by one of her students in the coming months for better understanding for her style.

To me, Madhaviji's style is very contained. While her movements are executed within the frame of one's body, the emotive aspect of the dance in her style is necessarily restrained. Her movement approach lacks the strong masculinity which Nrityagram, and often Sharmilaji, distinctly favour. I would term it as being more introvert. Also what is distinctly different is the lack of use of Agrachala (forward) and Prishthachala (backward) movements of the torso. Some illustrations of her basic steps as follows –

- One 3rd beat, with the brush of heel as leg is lifted to uttolita ⁽⁵⁾
torso shifts to opposite side with neck and eyes following the arm of the same side as the lifted uttolita

= TRIBHANGI NO. 6

Abhanga basic posture with anukunchita pada/kunchita pada

= TRIBHANGI NO. 7

ILEANA CITARISTI STYLE

The first thing that I found familiar was the basic steps. She practises and teaches the same set of basics which I learnt in Nrityagram. Some differences in hand and wrist movements as also the eyes exist. Ileanaji also makes use of isolated torso movement in her dance. A very clear example is her rendition of Khamaaj Pallavi which can be viewed at the following link –

www.youtube.com/watch?v=DaxL_iwgXjw

Bhramaris as she practises and teaches are also similar to the ones I learnt in Nrityagram, with a few additions in the Nrityagram style. That she strictly follows Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra's style of teaching is evident particularly when she is correcting dancers in her choreography. For an understanding of her creative process, please refer to DVD 2 and 3.

I have earlier submitted 3 DVDs as part of this report –

1. DVD 1 contains the stylistic differences between Nrityagram (my Alma Mater), Sharmilaji and Madhaviji's style as I have understood through actual dancing of the various basic steps practised in these individual styles, on my body. In the end, some of Ileanaji's disciples demonstrate a few of the basic steps they practise.
2. DVD 2 contains all the videos pertaining to the teaching and training methodology followed by Ileanaji for different age group of students. Here, warm up exercises, bhramaris, chaaris, Hasta mudras and viniyogs are demonstrated.
3. DVD 3 contains a pallavi choreographed by Ileanaji which she herself dances and later explains its concept. It also contains a comparative demonstration of Chaaris of the Nrityagram (danced by me) and Ileanaji's style (danced by one of her students). It concludes with an interview of Ileanaji.

My work with Ileanaji is still incomplete. I am yet to record an abhinaya piece choreographed by her and also complete the interview.

Meanwhile, because Ileanaji said that she would take some time to work on the new abhinaya piece which she would like me to record, I decided to start my first round of interaction with Jhelum Paranjape in Mumbai. I have visited her once and although I have documented some of her classes, it would only be meaningful when submit all together once I have completed with her. So it will be part of my 2nd report.

I conclude my report once again with Dr. Priyambada Mohanty Hejmadi's words –

“Although Odissi has established itself as a classical dance on the international scene, very little published material is available on the making of the dance, especially on the teachers who built it up.”

I do believe, having gone through the process myself, that after Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra, his disciples have continued to build the dance form with their individual contributions, drawing from various sources as the master himself did. And I wish to document these contributions and contribute in my own way to the lacuna existing, even today, so obviously in the published material on Odissi.

SECOND REPORT

‘It is the nature of the classical forms of Indian dancing that while they remain ancient and unchangeable on one level, they continue to grow or decline and certainly modify and assimilate new elements everyday’. These insightful words of Dr. Kapila Vatsyayan hold true not only for the style of Odissi dance in the current times that one witnesses being practised and performed today, but more specifically in the case of Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra’s tradition and its evolution over the years.

The important question is – What is Kelubabu’s style of Odissi? What are its peculiarities? What makes it unique that appropriates and therefore justifies its recognition as a distinct dance tradition comprising of definable movement aesthetics, grammar and basic technique? These are some of the many pertinent questions that one is faced with when one attempts to analyse and put on paper the nuances of Guruji’s style of moving. And I say ‘moving’ here, instead of ‘movement’ because it is the way in which a particular movement is rendered rather than the movement itself, that defines a specific style, school or gharana.

As I commence into this detailed analysis, I would first and foremost like to bring attention to the very fact that the hallmark of Kelubabu’s tradition of Odissi is subtlety and exceptional attention to detail. This is obvious not only in his various compositions, whether pallavis or abhinaya pieces, but even in the very basic chowk and tribhangi steps.

Having interacted with some of his renowned disciples over the past eight years, more recently with Jhelum Paranjape, I can now speak with certainty and considerable clarity about the basic technique as devised by Guruji himself for the Odissi dance form.

Overall technique specifics –

- Isolated torso movement is a distinct feature of Guruji’s style. The torso is moved always after the stamp of the foot at any time, no matter how fast the speed is, never with any jerk and almost always following a path of downward or upward arch.

Shoulder movement is restricted as the torso movement is initiated from the lower ribcage area

- The body alignment in the chowk basic posture is such that the spine is held erect with an imaginary straight line running down from the crown of the head through the tail bone till the mid point between heels of the feet in chowk position, with any tendency to push either the torso forward or the hip back which would otherwise alter this straight line, being consciously curbed. The weight is centred and balanced equally on both feet, the entire posture resembling the outlines of a square
- The body alignment in the tribhangi basic posture follows the Zee principle of temple sculptures with the entire body weight resting on the back standing foot of trasya pada such that the front foot is free to move. Three bends at the neck, at the waist and at the knee, with the torso and head tilted to either side, give shape to this stance
- Wrist movement is also a distinct feature. The wrist movements are delicate and always in synchrony with the timing of the torso. Again never with a jerk, the wrist is moved with exercised control
- At any time a leg movement is always initiated from the pelvic joint and never from the knee keeping the hip steady and without any dipping of either knees or the pelvis during movements such that the pelvis is held at the same seated level, whether in chowk, trasya or kumbha pada, unless in samabhanga posture

Note: I must mention here that these technical specificities were emphasised upon with equal importance by all the choreographers while teaching, with only Madhaviji differing in the use of torso

Chowk and Tribhangi Specific Basics -

Two standard sets of 10 movements in the chowk basic stance and 10 movements in the tribhangi basic stance have been formulated by Guruji which are to be practised as basic steps. These two sets consisting in total of 20 movement

patterns form the very core of his movement aesthetics and define with utmost clarity and precision the manner in which the body is to move while executing these steps.

It is indeed of primary importance that before beginning to teach Guruji's stylistic specifics, one should inform oneself of the nuances embedded in these 20 movement patterns with as much perfection as is possible. Every image that each step is inspired from and therefore attempts to recreate, every minute wrist movement, every shift of torso accompanied by the respective neck and glance variation must be accurately ascertained. It is only when one is confident of the grammatical details of the parent style, that one is able to identify a modification, however slight – be it in the neck, glance, wrist, torso, gesture, and understand through comparison the difference in nuance that either brings to the same movement pattern.

Thus expanding on Dr. Vatsyayan's words, it will be appropriate to say that these 20 basic movement patterns in chowk and tribhangi are intrinsic to Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra's style and will forever remain its 'ancient and unchangeable' primary elements while the various modifications, however minute, to these as also the new patterns/steps devised by some of his thinking disciples through the incorporation of new elements have helped the Guruji's style evolve and 'continue to grow'.

And no matter how each sub style has evolved and despite the input of individual aesthetic sensibilities into their movement patterns by each choreographer, there exists a common thread runs continuously across all these sub styles – Nrityagram, Madhavi Mudgal, Sharmila Biswas, Ileana Citaristi, Jhelum Paranjape – one that brings them all together under one umbrella. And this thread is the way in which the body is trained so that the energy moves seamlessly, **like water in a container**, in any given movement. **To understand this better, I have earlier submitted DVDs of which DVD 1& 2 pertain to Jhelum Paranjape's understanding of Guruji's technique. DVD 3 documents Jhelum ji's interview in which she shares her journey as Guruji's disciple, as an individual artist and choreographer.**

The 10 chowk and 10 tribhangi movement patterns as devised by Guruji are illustrated and explained below –

CHOWK NO I

①

- Jump in chowk pada with both legs off the floor
- Legs lifted from pelvic joint

CHOWK NO II

- Torso moves in the opposite direction after stamp of foot
- Neck and eyes move opposite to torso shift
- Wrist presses the palm down from vertical position facing inward.

CHOWK NO III

- 2nd foot on either side is stamped keeping the heels of other foot as is
- torso, eyes, neck move in 4th beat after stamp on 3rd beat on either side
- Hand is raised ~~over~~ from 1st beat itself on either side

To be repeated on other side

CHOWK NO IV

- In 2nd step, the chowk stance is wider, more distance between feet
- Torso shifts only after placing prskithadharu pada
- Eyes follow the hand movement throughout

To be repeated on other side

CHOWK NO V

- dancer changes the side she is facing on 1st beat turning 90°
- Turne 90° back to face front on 3rd beat
- 1st & 2nd steps are chowk No II
- 3rd step onwards torso and wrist do a circular movement to finish neutral, footwork same as chowk no III

CHOWK NO VI

- Every 4th beat has no footwork
- Head and eyes follow the hand movement on either side, both arms move
- 3rd step has transition of poshthadhanu to uttolita via ghanshita pada
- At no point are elbows locked to make the hands straight
- Every 6th step, torso becomes neutral

CHOWK NO VII

To be repeated on other side

- The working arm holds mayura and does a complete circle
- Torso following the hand also does a complete circle
- Hand and eyes follow hand
- In the last three steps the wrist holding mayura does a small circle to finish in chowk position with mayura held upright
- Body bends backwards while circling with arm

CHOWK NO VIII

To be repeated on other side

- Working hand does a complete circle in front of the body to finish in the same position as it started
- Pataka changes to kataka mukha at dhanupada to alapadma in last three steps.
- Head and eyes follow circling hand

CHOWK NO IX

To be repeated on other side

- On 3rd step body turns 90° to face side
- 1st two steps facing front and same as chowk no. II
- 3rd step onwards working hand holds mayura
- Torso does a small figure of eight along with arm and wrist circle to returna facing front from side
- From 3rd step head and eyes follow mayura

CHOWK NO X

- When repeating on other side, opposite hand is held out
- The pelvis remains the same level of height throughout the entire exercise

- Torso movement occurs with wrist movement
- Right hand is held at navel with shikharu
- Left hand in dola hasta position holds hanusarya with palm facing up
- Left wrist moves up and down with side to side torso movement

TRIBHANGI NO I

- Torso starts moving only after the stamp of foot from tribhanga to arabhanga till 2nd beat
- 3rd & 4th beat torso gradually moves back to tribhanga
- Neck and eyes move at the same pace of torso but in opposite direction
- Shikhara in both hands, one held at waist and other at mid thigh

TRIBHANGI NO II

- Torso, neck, eyes, wrist shift from one position to another over 2 beats
- Working leg lifted from pelvic joint to be placed in kunchita or vilaghnapaishini

- Toe or kunchita pada is placed in the position of heel of trasya pada of same foot, heel placed in the position of toe of trasya
- Hand opposite to working leg is held out in dola hasta position with hamsasya palm facing up, other hand shikhara at ~~navel~~ navel
- With kunchita, wrist moves up, torso in tribhanga, eyes & neck opposite to torso indicating the raised wrist
- With heel or vilaghnapaishini pada, wrist moves down, torso shifts to arabhanga, neck and eyes away from wrist

TRIBHANGI NO III

- Although footwork finishes on 3rd beat, torso with neck and eyes and wrist finish on 4th beat.

- Hand corresponding to working leg is held up at head level as if holding a mirror, other hand held in dola hasta
- With heel, torso shifts to arabhanga, neck and eyes move opposite to torso indicating raised hand holding hamsasya
- With heel, wrist holding hamsasya is pushed out, palm facing out
- On 3rd beat, wrist turned around so that hamsasya palm now faces the head, torso shifts to tribhanga, neck and eyes away from hamsasya to other direction

TRIBHANGI NO III

- Torso starts at tribhanga ^{with dharu pada} and shifts to arabhanga after stamp on 3rd beat
- Hands hold shukachanchu at chin and suchi to elbow of shukachanchu arm
- Neck and eyes move opposite to torso

TRIBHANGI NO IV

- Starting with trasya pada on one side, the dancer finishes with trasya on the other side.

- Both legs in circular motion, from in to out using lolita pada to lift, circle out and place in vilaghaaparshini; from out to in using ultolita pada to lift circle in to place in opposite trasya pada
- At all time, the level of pelvis is restricted to one level
- The most important point is to not allow the hip to shift to any side but hold it steady and use the torso to initiate every movement
- Hands held in shukachanchu at chin and suchi at elbow of shukachanchu arm
- Very controlled leg movement working entirely from pelvic joint

TRIBHANGI NO V

- In the 1st beat, the entire upper body does a complete circle initiated by the torso and lead by the circling hand, foot stamps in trasya.
- Head and eyes follow the circling hand, body turned 90° to side.
- Both hands hold mayura, static arm holds mayura upright in chowk position, circling hand holds mayura and starts from the static mayura.
- In 2nd beat, body turns back from side to front 90° with the right trasya changing to left trasya by shifting heels during turn.
- In 3rd beat, right heel is placed with knee facing front and circling mayura taken to static mayura.
- Last position has circling mayura finishing at waist pointing to the waist with corresponding foot in trasya on same side.

TRIBHANGI NO VI

- Both hands hold hamsasya, one raised to head level, other at waist as if holding two mirrors, palms facing body at 1st beat.
- With brush of heel on 3rd step, both wrists circle out and push away so that palms are facing out, torso shifts to arabhanga.
- In last 3 steps, wrists circle back in to initial position and torso shifts back to tribhanga, movement occurs after placing heel.
- Neck and eyes start from lower hamsasya at ^{KUNCHITA} Ahimsa, shift to upper hamsasya with heel brush & uttolita pada and finish at upper hamsasya in tribhanga on last trasya pada.

TRIBHANGI NO VII

- Starting with kunchita on one side, the movement finishes with trasya and tribhanga posture on other side
- While shifting from one side to the other in the final step, hip is controlled and prevented from jerking to other side, instead torso initiates the change over
- Both hands hold pataka and wrist moves with torso as in chank. no II, so do neck and eyes
- Movement gives the image of picking up a pot of water and placing in on the side of hip to walk, hence very graceful with no jerk of either torso or hands
- With kunchita, body is bent over with arabhanga and with ghanashita body shifts to tribhanga with uttolita and neck and eyes opposite to hands

TRIBHANGI NO VIII

- With 1st stamp on 1st beat, leg is lifted from pelvic joint to circle out using lolita pada to place in vilaghnapaschini on 2nd beat.
- Working hand holds mayura and circles from central line of body out in an upward arch, other hand is dola hasta
- Wrist leads the hand movement up above head and also while coming down to chank position

TRIBHANGI NO IX

- Working hand holds mayura, other dola hasta
- Wrist of mayura leads all hand movements
- While 1st and 2nd beats have neck and eyes following the mayura, the face is turned totally to mayura on 3rd beat while bending over as in chowk no VIII-2nd-beat
- No matter how fast the speed, the last foot must finish in traya pada

TRIBHANGI NO 8

- Right hand held at chin with Shukachanchu, left hand in hamsaeya above head
- With heel and brush of heel, torso shifts to arabhanga
- With traya and kunchita, torso shifts to tribhanga
- Neck and eyes move opposite to torso throughout.
- At every dhei, eyes are downcast
- Hip stays steady at one level

THIRD REPORT

In striving to discover the genuine and original portions of our great epic The Mahabharata, out of whose final form of 1,00,000 verses, only 24,000 seem to bear the stamp of originality of Vyasa, Sri Aurobindo, in his *The Mahabharata: Essays & Translations*, observes that

“One is struck in perusing the Mahabharata by the presence of a mass of poetry which bears the style and impress of a single, strong and original, even unusual mind, differing in his manner of expression, tone of thought & stamp of personality not only from every other Sanskrit poet we know but from every other great poet known to literature.”

He further notes that only a serious scrutiny of this great epic, when made with a deep sense of critical responsibility and according to the methods of patient scientific inference, will truly justify one in advancing any considerable theory on this magnanimous poetic structure.

Such may be said in unanimity in the case of the vast body of work created by Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra as well. And it must be noted here that mere physical practice of the dances composed by him, although one can never negate the fact that continuous repeated and rigorous practice is the very first step towards beginning to understand his aesthetic sensibilities, will never bring about an in-depth knowledge of what Kelubabu’s style is, for which one must truly attempt a serious scrutiny with considerable responsibility and with not only a scientific and systematic approach but also indefatigable attention to minute details.

For, as in poetry, and one must agree that Indian classical dance and therefore Kelubabu’s compositions are indeed poetry in motion, style and poetical personality must be not the only but the ultimate test of the genuineness of any of its verses.

And because the classical dances of India, and in this context specifically Kelubabu’s compositions, are not just poetry in motion but are indeed poetry in motion in response to the music it is set to, it is imperative that a language with codified grammar and technique be defined such that poetry may be composed in it. And to me, Kelubabu along with his many illustrious associates and collaborators did exactly this – he created a language in which we dancers of

today, and of generations to come, are and will continue to be not only able to speak through our body but also write our own stories.

And to be able to write our own stories in his language, we must have a firm grip on the technique of his way of moving as also an intimate feeling of his language, a sensitiveness to the shades & expression inherent to his style and most importantly, an instinctive feeling of what is or is not possible. The sensitiveness to these aspects of his language would vary, I must admit, only with the amount of education and natural fineness of taste of each individual dancer.

And it is evident in the choreographic approach of Jhelum Paranjape, particularly her interpretations of Marathi abhangs as one can see in DVD 1 & 2.

Often when a line in poetry, that is being interpreted and put to movement by a dancer, is similar to one already choreographed by Guruji, the dancer uses the same or similar movements to give life to her interpretation. Once in a rare while, one finds a dancer who, while writing in Kelubabu's language, creates her own imagery through her own interpretation never once deviating from or diluting the original style or aesthetic sensibility.

That, then, can be termed as genuine poetry bearing the indelible mark of the Master's language.

In my last 2 reports, I have dealt in depth with the technique or grammar of Kelubabu's style/language/way of moving as also those developed by some of his distinguished disciples.

Here, I would like to draw attention to the philosophy behind the Odissi repertoire. During the Jayantika days of the evolution of Odissi, much had been deliberated upon regarding the content and structure of the repertoire and finally it was decided that the format would be as follows –

Mangalacharan, Batu, Pallavi, Abhinaya, Mokshya Nata.

It must be mentioned here, for this is of prime importance in this context, that Kelubabu had sent his ace disciple Sanjukta Panigrahi to Kalakshetra to study the form of Bharatnatyam for three years. Dr. Mayadhar Rout, a key member of Jayantika and significant contributor to the evolution of the present day Odissi too had spent many years at Kalakshetra studying Bharatnatyam which later would help Jayantika in structuring the Odissi form and repertoire.

That Bharatnatyam influenced the technique and repertoire of Odissi is evident from the Jayantika records of which a particular report recording the proceedings of a meeting held on 29 August 1958 provides a detailed description of Batu nritya. The main points included –

- The item is to be dedicated to Shiva in the form of Batukeshwara Bhairava
- It should start with the dancer depicting musicians playing the veena, venu, mardala and manjeera
- It should include sthayi ukuta and a variety of khandi, Arasa and Muktai
- It should include Bhangi-s such as Darpana, Biraja, Kari hasta, Kati china, Abhimana, Parsva mandala with appropriate eyes and neck movements
- It should strictly not include Chakra bhramari

That Guru Debaprasad Das disagreed with this version, which came to be known as Kelu gharana, and preferred a version of Batu that proceeds almost like a varnam of the Bharatnatyam repertoire with alternating passages of nritta and sahitya, as also with the rest of the Odissi repertoire, is well recorded in the article ‘Technique and Repertoire’ by Mohan Khokar published in the Marg magazine in 1960.

The practice of Indian classical dance should lead the dancer from outside herself to within, physically, emotionally and spiritually, and it is to be able to achieve this, that the repertoire of every classical form is structured as such.

Balasaraswati, the doyen of Bharatnatyam, has explained this with utmost clarity. She speaks of the dancer as the devotee and the repertoire as the sacred temple: one enters through the gopuram or outer hall of Alarippu, crosses the Ardhamandapam of halfway hall of Jatiswaram, then the Mandapa or great hall of Shabdham, enters the holy precinct of the deity in Varnam, into the Garbha Griha or sanctum of Padam from its external precinct to the final burning of camphor accompanied by a measure of din and bustle in the concluding Tillana.

The Odissi repertoire too, as structured by Kelubabu, begins with Mangalacharan, an invocation by the dancer/devotee at the entrance to the temple, proceeds to circumambulate the temple structure depicting the exquisite physical beauty of the numerous postures in various bhangi-s sculpted on the temple walls through Batu, then advancing through the Natya Mandapa with the joyous Pallavi, enters the Garbha griha with the self-reflective Abhinaya, an Ashotapadi wherein she is

in private conversation with her Lord, finally leading to Moshya Nata, the dance of liberation. Thus, the repertoire leads the dancer from collective external consciousness to singular internal consciousness such that in Mokshya Nata a moment of absolute peace and stillness is reached when the dancer is in total union while in movement with her Atma or soul within.

The structure of the Odissi repertoire which was derived largely from the Bharatnatyam repertoire itself, therefore reflects not only the Bhakti Marga as proposed in Vishishtadvaita system of Indian philosophy but also follows the principles of Integral Yoga wherein the knowledge (of the form), works or action indicating continuous practice of the form, and devotion engaging the emotional and aesthetic powers of the individual, elevates the dancer from a mere physical to the transcendental platform where the intellect, body and soul unite with the Supreme through the dance.

Dance then becomes yoga itself.

FOURTH REPORT

In her introduction to Volume I of Kalaatattvakosa, Dr. Bettina Baumer states thus,

“The Indian arts, both in theory (Shastra) and practice (prayoga), are branches of a single living tree of Indian culture. They cannot be understood in isolation from other dimensions of thought and science, myth and ritual, spiritual and secular traditions. The underlying world-view has crystallized in certain concepts, reflecting the understanding of cosmos and man, of space and time, of form and structure, of the part and the whole, of body, senses and mind.”

Indian classical dance, as one of the prominent forms of the Indian arts, therefore reflects a distinctively Indian inter-disciplinary system in which the textual and the oral, the verbal and the visual as also the aural, the scientific and the metaphysical, the transcendental and the functional are interlocked as parts of a whole.

It is to re-discover, unearth from beneath heaps of isolated pieces of misinformed ‘knowledge’ on the classical dances, and explore independently this inter-disciplinary system embedded within, which would help further evolve my understanding of Indian classical dance in general and Odissi in particular, that I embarked on this journey, digging into the past. Over the past five years, the discoveries have often surprised me, confused me, propelled me to search a little more, all the while revealing to me the magnanimity of the classical dances and all the disciplines inter woven so intricately within its vast fabric. But this is only the beginning; much is left to delve into, to siphon through, to decipher in order to fathom its diversely nuanced aspects. For, as the Amritabindu Upanishad states, knowledge in a discipline of practice is assumed to be ‘already there’, hidden, waiting to be discovered which is why ‘the wise practitioner must carry out a churning operation within himself, employing his own mind, without respite as the churning agent’.

And thus the churning continues, this research being one of the many outcomes.

Very simply put, Indian classical dance has science at its very core while at the same time it is deeply rooted in Indian philosophy. Within its vast framework, a system of correspondence exists between the material, physical and the psychical, ethical as also spiritual. Synthesizing diverse disciplines, the classical dances have the ‘latency and the potency’ of bringing together all aspects of life – from the physical to the psychical and even metaphysical – into a meaningful whole. And it is through the refinement of the senses, sense perception particularly of the eye and ear, that Indian classical dance not only provides both pleasure and education but also, and perhaps more significantly, becomes a vehicle of beauty, duty and conduct.

And because the medium through which Indian classical dance is expressed is the human body, a dancer must have a fairly sound understanding of the body itself.

Anthropologist John Blacking asserts that there is no such thing as “the human body”.

There are many kinds of body which are shaped by the different environments and expectations of the societies nurturing them, and as environments and expectations change, so do the many kinds of body which the societies produce. A classical dance practitioner of today assumes a body in her practice, this ‘body’ being a palimpsest of not only traditional assumptions about body and practice but also of more recent paradigms and discourses of the body-in-practice.

One aspiring to become a master of the classical arts must therefore possess complete knowledge of the body, which traditionally implies acquiring knowledge of three different ‘bodies in practice’ –

- The fluid body of humours and saps
- The body composed of bones, muscles and vulnerable vital junctures
- The subtle, interior body

While the first two bodies are based on Ayurveda and together constitute the *Sthula Sharira*, the third – the *Suksma Sharira* – is understood to be encased within the physical body.

A dancer first learns her art as is taught to her; over time she discovers the means of mastering her sthula sharira, and it is only then that she is able to unlearn and

have command over her *suksma sharira* whence the art becomes her own and is no longer the one taught to her.

The process begins with repeated practice of the outer forms of exercise, considered as body preparation, which eventually renders the external body flexible and ‘flowing like a river’. And as the movements in dance ‘come correct’ the dancer should begin to manifest physical, mental and behavioural *lakshana* indicating change such that over time, the exercises and movements become internalised.

The art of teaching is a complex, interactive exchange in which the master continuously reads and re-reads the signs of a student’s progress in each movement. Similarly, in the guru’s practice the student witnesses the ‘inner life’ of each form or movement enlivened by the engagement of the master’s ‘life force’ or *prana vayu*. . This vital ‘inner life’ of each movement is assumed to be present as the seed of the form, implanted by the master during each first lesson. Over time, training and careful correction nurtures this seed, helps it sprout and grow. The student slowly discovers the correct form and attains it by becoming one with the original qualities of the character in movement. It is then that the student emerges as an artist who ‘becomes’ a form embodying the *bhava* appropriate to each movement or form she practises.

Understandably, the practice of Indian classical dance, like meditation, therefore tames and purifies the external *Sthula-Sharira* (the body composed of fluid, with humours and saps, as also of the bones, muscles and vital vulnerable junctures) as it quiets and balances the body’s three humours (*tridosha*, *tridhaatu*) – wind (*vata*), phlegm (*kapha*) and fire (*pitta*). Eventually the dancer should begin to discover the *Suksma Sharira* (the subtle, metaphysical interior body) within her which articulates the psycho-spiritual experiences similar to those of the yogi and the pilgrim or devotee visiting the temple. This subtle body, most often identified with *Kundalini Yoga*, is defined by one of the many scholars as “ an invisible mandala formed by a combination of symbolic (but also very real) geometric figures” and often depicted as a microcosm of the universe, with the *Shiva Samhita* noting, “All the beings that exist in the three worlds are also to be found in the subtle body”. Rightly, it is called the seat of the *Atma* or soul. And the discovery of this subtle body is made possible by the awakening of the vital *Kundalini* energy within the dancer’s body through long-term continuous dance practice, akin to yoga. This finds a very apt expression in the *Shiva Samhita* –

“where the Cosmic Energy – the aggregate of all Kundalinis – resides in inseparable union with Parama Shiva (Brahman, the Supreme Reality), and there merging her with the Cosmic Energy, the yogin is able to obtain spiritual release from the bondage of this world and everything worldly.....the yogin’s conscious identification of his self with his gross physical body ceases”

Thus the concept of Yoga in the world of classical Indian dance assumes much significance, for within its framework it brings about the essential equilibrium, balance, harmony of the physical, sensuous, emotive, intellectual and spiritual levels of the dance body.

Here the body becomes the primary tool, physically being made up of bones, joints, muscles. And it is the sense organs and sense perceptions that are the potent vehicles of feeling and sensibility. So the body and mind are interdependent and mutually effecting with senses, feeling and sensibility being fundamental. In other words, the dancer through her continuous practice must arrive at a very different view of the body than what is conventionally perceived as corporeal frame or fleshy mass. One finds mention of this ‘other’ view in the Atharva Veda as,

“The brain (medha) is called the reservoir of Brahman, the human body is the citadel of man. Because Brahman resides in this citadel of the human body, it is called Purusha”.

This relationship of the senses and the mind, the capacity of each to move inward and enlarge outward is expanded in the Kathopanishad as,

‘Higher than the senses (and their objects) is the mind; more excellent than the mind (manas), the intellect (sattvam); above the intellect soars the great soul (mahaatman) and higher than the great soul is the unmanifest (avyakta); and higher than the unmanifested is the Supreme soul (Purusha, also called Brahman)’.

The Upanishad, considered the most refined statement of a world view and speculation on the nature of the universe and the life of man, speaks of this conscious process of gradual refinement from one plane to the other with the need for restraint and discipline. The continuous dedicated practice of Indian classical dance brings about this gradual refinement in the dancer, not only as an artist but also as a human being, through purification of the ‘eye’ and the ‘ear’, the visual

and the aural wherein the purification is not merely ritual but is a constant endeavour to arrive at a higher and higher degree of subtlety and refinement with every passing moment within and without dance. On the same note, transcendence from the physical to the metaphysical through an intrinsic relationship and mutuality of mind, intellect, brain and body, while in movement, should lead to the experience of aesthetic delight or *rasaanubhuti*.

It would therefore be apt to quote here from the Shiva Sutra –

Nartaka Aatma/ Rangontaraatma//

The text describes Atman as the dancer or actor and the ‘inner soul of the subtle form’ or Antaraatman as the stage or ranga on which the dance or drama is performed. The concept of the Self enacting a dance or drama and ‘the inner soul’ or Jiva as distinct from the outer body, representing the stage or ranga is at once related to the philosophy of dance as well as to the cosmic view of the Self.

Upon analysing the components of classical Indian dance and music too, one recognises that the svaras, the raagas and the syllabic sounds possess the potential to awaken the metaphysical or the subtle body of not only the dancer but also the sahrdaya, sensitive spectator, leading both to experience the pleasure of actually performing and witnessing the performance respectively.

As the footwork synchronises with the musical notes, and the body movements and histrionic expression blend into the raga, the sangatis (a particular variation of a phrase in a song) and gamakas (oscillation of a note, a deliberate decoration to add grace and beauty) are also intricately woven into the body movements. The lines, angles, spatial patterns and rhythm of the dance movements, all in accordance with the taala of the music, echo the universal rhythm. Specific ragas, and specific syllables and svaras or notes evoke particular moods.

Every raaga, defined by the arrangement of svaras in ascending and descending order, acquires a distinctive character and mood. Sets of notes with defined relationships to one another are known to be associated with the various chakras and impact them positively thereby awakening the inherent representative characters of the chakras in both the performer and the spectator.

Research conducted to analyse the impact of music on the subtle human body reveals the definite association of the chakras to the corresponding specific Bija Mantras, raagas and svaras as presented in the following table –

CHAKRAS	Bija Mantras	Svaras	Raagas
Muladhara	Lam	Shadja (Saa)	Hindol, Shyam-kalyan
Svadhishthana	Vam	Komal Rishabh (re) Shuddha Rishabh (Re)	Hamsadhwani, Gurjari Todi, Yaman
Manipura	Ram	Komal Gandhaar (ga) Shiddha Gandhaar (Ga)	Abhogi, Bhimpalas, Bahtiyaar, Bibhaas, Lalit, Gunakali
Anahata	Yam	Shuddha Madhyam (Ma) Teevra Madhyam (*Ma)	Bhairav, Ahir Bhairav, Durga
Vishuddhi	Ham	Pancham (Pa)	Jayjayanti, Des
Agnya	Ksham	Komal Dhaivat (dha) Shuddha Dhaivat (Dha)	Bageshri, Bhup
Sahasrara		Komal Nishaad (ni) Shuddha Nishaad (Ni)	Durbari, Bhairavi

Emotion is said to be generated by the raagas constituted of particular svara structures which in turn are embellished further by the gamakas with their varying pitch, timbre and volume. These ragas with their constituent svaras possess the ability to influence the metaphysical apparatus of the human body while simultaneously adorning the execution of dance movements. And because music is of prime importance in the context of Indian classical dance, the dancer through her body elaborates the meaning of the words being sung and expands on their myriad connotations and deeper undertones. In the highest form of expression, the dancer sings with her body.

Hindu Temple and the Structure of Human Body: Comparison

It is but obvious then that the arts occupy an intermediate position mediating between metaphysics and physics, between spirituality and science. The Purusha Sukta gives a vivid account of the cosmic man and lays the foundation for comprehending the 'human', the anatomical and physiological, physical, social and cosmic man. 'Man', cosmic or human, has a defined structure with the parts and the whole again inter-related and interlocked. And a Hindu temple, in all its sculptural and architectural magnificence, represents a whole metaphysical conception and at the same time its building requires the science and technology of architecture and engineering, thus necessitating an indispensably interdisciplinary approach.

The vast Hindu canonical literature on Devalaya Vastu and sacred geography describe the temple as a cosmic man, the 'Purusha'. The ancient Indian text on Vastu Shastra (traditional science of architecture), the Mayamatam, refers the Vastu Purusha as the presiding deity of all land structures meant for temple or house. The ground plan, the Vastu Purusha Mandala is the metaphysical plan of the temple incorporating the course of heavenly bodies and supernatural forces.

The name Vastu Purusha Mandala essentially consists of three parts – Vastu, Purusha and Mandala. Stella Kramrisch, in her monumental work and certainly one of the most authoritative on Hindu temple architecture, THE HINDU TEMPLE, explains these thus –

Vastu is the extent of Existence in its ordered state and is likened to the Purusha, the Supernal or Cosmic Man, whose image is congruous and identical to the planned site.

Purusha, the Cosmic Man, is the origin and source of Existence (Aparaa-prakriti) and is known to the world as the manifested aspect of Himself, the Paraa-prakriti,

the immutable Supreme One. In his identity with the plan, Purusha is shown in his conditioned aspect. While Mandala, in general, denotes any closed polygon, the Vastupurushamandala specifically is a square which is its essential form. It could also be converted into a triangle, hexagon, octagon and circle of equal area and still retain its symbolism. Describing it as the magic diagram (yantra) and the form (rupa) of the

Vastupurusha, Kamrisch further elaborates,

“It is his body (sharira) and a bodily device (sharira yantra) by which those who have the requisite knowledge attain the best results in temple building, It is laid out in tabular notation as man (naraprastara) and site (vaastuprastara).

In the Purusha, Supernal man, the Supreme Principle is beheld. Beyond form and non-contingent, it is beyond description. It is known by intellectual intuition as residing in man, the microcosm, and in the universe, the macrocosm. Either is its place of manifestation. Man and Universe are equivalent in this their indwelling centre. Of this equivalence the Purusha is an image. In the Purusha, the relation of the Supreme Principle (Brahman) and of manifestation is seen as coterminous.....It is the site indwelt, and pervaded by the Purusha.....By its impress that piece of land, freed of all associations acts as primordial, undifferentiated substance (Prakriti).”

The terms Brahman, Purusha and Atman are almost all-pervading in Indian culture and thought, and in spite of their apparent abstractness, they have greatly influenced the theory and practice of the arts. These three concepts belong to the supreme or transcendent level (para). Passing from the inner or abstract to the outer or concrete stands Sharira, the body in all its gross and subtle dimensions. The first mediator between the metaphysical and the physical is Praana, life and breadth, the vital energy. So also Bija, the seed of vegetal, animal and human life, occupies an intermediate position, having both a physical, a symbolical and even mystical meaning (paraapara). Coming down to the expression in external forms (apara level), the first step is the characteristic feature, the sign by which we recognise and identify an object – lakshana. The external manifestation of abstract or symbolical ideas is the work of art which combines the idea with a form, and which involves skill in treating a material – Shilpa. The creation of a beautiful form cannot be separated from its creator, hence Shilpin, the artist/artisan and the qualities he incorporates, has also to be treated along with his art.

Thus, in the context of my research, here Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra is the Shilpin whose creation of a beautiful form – the present day Odissi dance in this case – along with the qualities he has aesthetically incorporated, is the very focus of debate, discussion and further study.

In order to comprehend and appreciate his creation, one must first acknowledge that Kelucharan Mahapatra’s artistic journey touches every key aspect of the cultural life of Odisha. His evolution as an artist is also a historical record of the evolution of Odissi from the temple to the proscenium stage as a prominent classical form of India. Be it the traditional expertise of the Chitrakars, or the entertaining art forms of Gotipua and Jatra parties, or the Ras Leela performances soaked in bhakti, or the innovations attempted at the Annapurna Theatre Groups,

all these experiences, acquired not through formal training but through a continuous interaction with life, contributed richly to his understanding and creation of the Odissi form. Such was his dedicated search for excellence that every action of his, whether building a wall, constructing a roof or composing a delicate dance piece to Jayadeva's lyrics, was permeated by the same degree of intensity and artistry. It is obvious then that such a perfectionist as him would settle for anything less whether from his students or from his fellow musicians and scholars. And it is the magnanimous presence and personality of this great Guru, his detailed teaching and in depth insights into the entire panorama of Odia culture, that have drawn dancers from across the world to his door to learn his art from him, and continue to attract unfortunate ones like me, who have not had the fortune of seeking knowledge from the Master himself. And it is for the very same reasons that his distinguished disciples, some of whom I have had the privilege of interacting with during the course of this research, continue to practise, teach, choreograph and perform with as much dedication and perfection as the Guru himself. Upon careful observation and patient analysis, one will find that in the works of all his disciples, there flows a continuous fine thread of aesthetic sensibility and refinement, not just of movements but also of the thought behind each, that they have imbibed from the Master himself and that which will remain ingrained in their psyche guiding them throughout their individual journeys not just as Odissi dancers but as sensible and sensitive artists.

Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra seeks to bring about this refinement within every dancer through the practise and performance of the Odissi repertoire wherein the dancer begins with Mangalacharan, an invocation at the entrance to the temple, proceeds to circumambulate the temple structure depicting the exquisite physical beauty of the numerous postures in various bhangi-s sculpted on the temple walls through Batu, then advancing through the Natya Mandapa with the joyous Pallavi, enters the Garbha griha with the self-reflective Abhinaya, an Ashatapadi wherein she is in private conversation with her Lord, finally leading to Moshya Nata, the dance of liberation. Thus, the repertoire leads the dancer from collective external consciousness to singular internal consciousness such that in Mokshya Nata a moment of absolute peace and stillness is reached when the dancer is in total union while in movement with her Atma or soul within. The Dancer, then becomes the Yogi herself.

And just as the construction of a temple requires the expertise of a Sthapaka for the correct planning and execution in its construction, so also in dance, does the

shishya require the vigilant guidance of such a knowledgeable Guru who, with the correct training, would mould her body and mind into the perfect vehicle for delivering the art in its truest form. And it is to become knowledgeable so as to be able to hand over the knowledge of this art with adequate integrity to upcoming dancers, that I chose to go beyond the mere physicality of Indian classical dance in general, and Odissi in particular, through this research.

It would perhaps be apt to end with Dr. Stella Kamrisch's words about the Sthapaka, the architect-priest who is to have the qualification of an *Acharya*, the one who knows the essence of the sacred texts – the Vedas and Agamas. Stella Kamrisch says,

“The architect of the temple was not only a master of the ‘ocean of the science of architecture’. Balanced in body and mind, he had to be versed in the traditional science (shastra) in its various branches, and as much in the knowledge of rhythms (chhandas), mathematics and astronomy as in the conditions of different places, etc (*Samaraanganasutradhaara* – a treatise on architecture). The various arts and sciences had to be known for one and same purpose, so that he could apply in his work which was to be an image and reconstitution of the universe.”

Guru Kelucharan Mahapatra is one among many such great Acharyas that India takes enormous pride in. One can aspire and only attempt to emulate him.

Ayona Bhaduri
January 2018, Kolkata

P.S. With this final report I am enclosing 2 DVDs pertaining to this research. These contain excerpts compiled from DVDs submitted with previous reports over the past 2 years.

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